

Studies on Cyclic Thioketones. Part I. Synthesis of Non-polymerised Thiocyclohexanone, Thiocyclopentanone and their Derivatives.

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The present paper describes the synthesis of thiocyclohexanone, thiocyclopentanone and their derivatives. These thioketones have been prepared by passing a simultaneous current of dry HCl and H₂S into an alcoholic solution of the corresponding ketones (*cf.* Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 647; *Science and Culture*, 1935, 1, 158, 435). Fromm (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 2090) isolated tripolymerised thio derivatives by passing a successive current of HCl and H₂S into alcoholic solutions of cyclohexanone, cyclopentanone and *p*-methylcyclohexanone.

Trithiocyclohexanone (I), as isolated by Fromm is a cyclic thioether and it does not react with phenylhydrazine, hydroxylamine, semicarbazide etc., nor can it be acylated or alkylated.

The function of hydrochloric acid in these cases seems to be three-fold; it acts (*i*) as a condensing agent, (*ii*) as a dehydrating agent and (*iii*) as a polymerising agent. Hence, Fromm could not isolate non-polymerised thioketones by passing successive currents of H₂S and HCl on account of accumulation of large excess of HCl. Non-polymerised thioketones could be isolated by taking out the thioketones as soon as they are formed from the zone of reaction, thus avoiding the influence of excess of HCl.

These thioketones when freshly distilled, are pink in colour, and the colour slowly changes to orange and finally disappears after a few days, but on redistillation, the pink colour reappears. If the pink colour be due to the chromophoric C : S group, then it follows

that unlike cyclic ketones or ketonic esters, the thiolic phase of the cyclic thioketones is more stable at the ordinary temperature.

The 'thio-thiol' tautomerism in the above compounds, analogous to 'keto-enol' tautomerism in the corresponding ketones, has been observed and approximately estimated by iodometric method, Meyer's method of keto-enol estimation not being suitable.

The iodometric method depends on the fact that the C-SH group will be oxidised whereas the C:S group will remain unchanged and that the addition of iodine to the double bond will be negligible compared to the oxidation of the thiol groups.

The formation of phenylhydrazones and semicarbazones identical with those of the corresponding ketones manifests the ketonic behaviour of the cyclic thioketones and it has been observed that the freshly distilled red liquids react more readily than the colourless thiolic varieties. Both thiocyclohexanone and thiocyclopentanone have been acetylated by the action of acetic anhydride in presence of sodium acetate giving S-acetyl derivatives since the products are coloured and since the acetyl groups are removed by phenylhydrazine in the cold producing acetyl phenylhydrazine and the phenyl hydrazones of the corresponding thioketones with evolution of H₂S.

The cyclohexanone phenylhydrazone has also been converted to tetrahydrocarbazole by the action of dilute hydrochloric acid (*cf.* Bayer, *Annalen*, 1894, 278, 106; Dreschel, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, ii, 38, 67).

It has also been possible to prepare a colourless S-methyl derivative from the thiocyclohexanone and it reacts with phenylhydrazine and gives methylmercaptan and cyclohexanone phenylhydrazone.

It is noteworthy that the acetylated thioketones have got normal

molecular weights in benzene (cryoscopic) whereas the parent compounds have molecular weights corresponding to nearly one and half times their normal values. This suggests that in benzene these free cyclic thioketones are most probably partly associated at low temperatures. However, it was not possible to determine the molecular weights by the boiling point method due to constant fluctuation of temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiocyclohexanone.—A solution of *cyclohexanone* (50 g.) in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) was treated with a current of dry hydrochloric acid and dry sulphuretted hydrogen in the same manner as described in the case of thiocamphor (*cf.* Sen, *loc. cit.*). The solution slowly changed to deep red and suddenly after 1-1½ hours became turbid owing to the precipitation of an insoluble oil. The emulsion was treated with ice-cold water and extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was washed with water and sodium bicarbonate solution, dried over sodium sulphate, ether removed and the liquid distilled at 76°/15 mm., unchanged *cyclohexanone* distilling at 45°/15 mm. Higher boiling fractions were also obtained whose investigations are not yet complete.

It is a heavy red oil having a slight mercaptanic smell, the colour slowly changing on keeping and ultimately becoming colourless. It slowly polymerises but the tripolymerised derivative is not easily formed without the agency of hydrochloric acid. It is insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in alcohol, but readily soluble in benzene, chloroform, ether, etc. It forms a yellow sodium salt with metallic sodium and a yellowish brown lead salt with lead acetate which immediately changes to black. [Found: C, 63.25; H, 8.65; S, 28.05; M.W. (in benzene, cryoscopic) 162. $C_6H_{10}S$ requires C, 63.16; H, 8.77; S, 28.07 per cent. M.W., 114).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the action of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium hydroxide, melts at 166°-67° (mixed m.p. with *cyclohexanone semicarbazone*). (Found: N, 26.81. Calc. for $C_7H_{13}ON_3$: N, 27.09 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* was prepared by adding calculated amount of phenylhydrazine to the thioketone and keeping the mixture at the ordinary temperature overnight, when the liquid solidified and H_2S was evolved. Excess of phenylhydrazine was removed by washing

with ether and the residue was crystallised from alcohol as plates, m.p. 75-76° (decomp.) (mixed m.p. with *cyclohexanone phenylhydrazone*). (Found: N, 14.85. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{16}N_2$: N, 14.89 per cent). The phenylhydrazone with moderately concentrated hydrochloric acid forms *tetrahydrocarbazole*, which is obtained from *cyclohexanone phenylhydrazone*. It crystallises from alcohol as needles, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 83.72; H, 7.8; N, 8.15. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{13}N$: C, 84.21; H, 7.6; N, 8.19 per cent).

If the current of the two gases be continued for 3 hours, the whole solution becomes solid, which after crystallisation melts at 102°. It has been identified to be the trithio derivative of From (*loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 63.4; H, 8.71; S, 28.2; M.W. 348. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{30}S_3$: C, 63.16; H, 8.77; S, 28.07 per cent. M.W. 342).

Methylation of Thiocyclohexanone: Methylcyclohexane monosulphide.—An ethereal solution of thiocyclohexanone (10 g.) containing a few drops of alcohol was treated with metallic sodium (2.2 g.) in thin slices. The mixture was treated with methyl iodide (10 g.) and heated at 60°-70° for 2 hours. The solution was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. From the ethereal solution the methyl derivative was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 55°/15 mm. having a characteristic smell, yield 6 g.

The substance decolourises bromine water and dilute permanganate solution in cold. It does not form any precipitate with lead acetate. With phenylhydrazine it forms methyl mercaptan and *cyclohexanone phenylhydrazone*. (Found: C, 65.25; H, 9.5; S, 24.85. $C_7H_{12}S$ requires, C, 65.62; H, 9.38; S, 25.0 per cent).

Acetylation of Thiocyclohexanone.—Thiocyclohexanone (10 g.), was heated with acetic anhydride (25 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (5 g.) for one hour. The oil, separating on pouring the solution into water and making alkaline with sodium carbonate, was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution, dried over sodium sulphate, ether removed and then distilled at 85°/10 mm. It has an ester like smell, slightly pungent and on treatment with phenylhydrazine forms acetylated phenylhydrazine and *cyclohexanone phenylhydrazone* with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. It decolourises dilute bromine water and dilute permanganate solution in cold. (Found: C, 61.15; H, 8.05; S, 20.32; M.W. 159. $C_8H_{12}OS$ requires C, 61.54; H, 7.7; S, 20.51 per cent. M.W., 156).

Thiocyclopentanone was prepared in a similar manner as described in the case of thiocyclohexanone. Its odour is strongly

mercaptanic. The tendency of formation of tripolymerised derivative is much greater in this case than in the case of thiocyclohexanone. The insoluble red oil separates out in the course of 1-1½ hour, and even if it be treated just after the formation of emulsion by means of ice-cold water, nearly 5% of the material is changed into the tripolymerised derivative. It boils at 86°-88°/10 mm. (Found: C, 59.73; H, 8.25; S, 32.12; M.W. 142. C₅H₈S requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0; S, 32.0 per cent. M.W., 100). The tripolymerised derivative crystallises from alcohol as white shiny plates, m.p. 99°. (Found: C, 59.55; H, 7.99; S, 32.03; M.W., 310. Calc. for C₁₅H₂₄S₃: C, 60.0; H, 8.0; S, 32.0 per cent M.W., 300).

The *oxime* melts at 56°-57° (mixed m.p. with cyclopentanone oxime). (Found: N, 14.23. Calc. for C₅H₉ON: N, 14.14 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was very slowly formed by heating thiocyclopentanone with semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium hydroxide for 3-4 hours on the water-bath. It crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 212°-13° (mixed m.p. with cyclopentanone semicarbazone, Wallach, *Annalen*, 1907, 353, 308). (Found: N, 30.31; Calc. for C₆H₁₁ON₃: N, 29.8 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, obtained in the same manner as in the case of thiocyclohexanone, is a pungent smelling liquid, b.p. 67°/8mm. With phenylhydrazine in cold it gives acetyl phenylhydrazine (m.p. 128°), with evolution of H₂S, and a liquid (not isolated). (Found: C, 58.98; H, 7.21; S, 22.35; M.W. 142. C₇H₁₀OS requires, C, 59.15; H, 7.04; S, 22.53 per cent. M.W. 142).

Estimation of the Amount of Thiocyclohexanone in the thiolic phase.—Thiocyclohexanone (0.4-0.5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (50 c.c.) and heated with 25 c.c. of N/10-alcoholic solution of iodine at 10° and allowed to stand, the solution being constantly shaken. The excess of iodine was then titrated against N/10-sodium thiosulphate. 1 C.c. iodine absorbed = 0.0114 g. of thiocyclohexanone in the thiolic phase. The results found are 38% thiol in the freshly distilled sample and 70% after 1 hour.

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